

ACADEMIC TRACK OF FOSS4G EUROPE 2017 – OPEN INNOVATION FOR EUROPE

M. A. Brovelli ^{a,*}, D. Kotzinos ^b, N. Paparoditis ^c, V. Raghavan ^d

^a Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, Milano, Italy, maria.brovelli@polimi.it

^b Lab. ETIS UMR 8051, University Paris-Seine, Univ. Cergy-Pontoise, ENSEA, CNRS, Cergy-Pontoise, France,
dimitrios.kotzinos@u-cergy.fr

^c University Paris Est, IGN, ENSG, Champs-sur-Marne, France, nicolas.paparoditis@ign.fr

^d Media Center, University Osaka City, Osaka, Japan, raghavan@media.osaka-cu.ac.jp

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PREFACE

FOSS4G-Europe, also called FOSS4G-EU, is a major European conference on Free and Open Source Geospatial technologies. The conference aims to bring FOSS4G users and developers together and to foster closer interactions within the European geospatial communities.

FOSS4G-Europe 2017 was held at Ecole Nationale des Sciences Géographiques (ENSG) in Marne La Vallée, France, from July 18th to 22nd, 2017.

FOSS4G-Europe hosts an Academic Track (AT) which ran as a dedicated session over the three days of the conference. This AT was co-organised by ISPRS, ICA and OSGEO. Through an open-call for papers, FOSS4G-Europe invited original research contributions covering all aspects of FOSS4G and its application. Submissions focusing on INSPIRE, Big Data and Societal Challenges were particularly encouraged. A variety of topics such as on results achieved, case studies, work in progress, and demos were welcome. However, mere presentations of technology or use cases without properly justifying originality with respect to the state of the art and lacking particular novelty were discouraged.

38 papers were submitted to the academic track and were blind reviewed by 3 reviewers. Finally 28 papers were selected for publication in this volume of the ISPRS Archives.

The editors wish to thank all contributing authors and the reviewers for their excellent work.

We sincerely hope that this volume provides a useful insight on the high potential of FOSS4G to deliver and deploy geospatial solutions of high scientific and societal value.

* Corresponding author

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